

ANALYSIS OF MOLDAVIAN AND ROMANIAN FEMININE PROPER NAMES OF LATIN ORIGIN

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Abstract

The research object of the present article deals with the Moldavian and Romanian feminine proper names of Latin origin, which were canonized by the Catholic Church. The observation is carried out on the corpus of fifty-three feminine anthroponyms.

Every one of those fifty-three Moldavian and Romanian feminine names is derived from another proper name and that is why they are classified according to the main characteristics of the anthroponym used as a basis during the process of derivation, i. e. if it is masculine or feminine by gender, if it is Latin or Moldavian/Romanian by origin.

Keywords: *Moldavian/Romanian feminine personal name, Latin origin, canonized.*

The research object of the present text is Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal names of Latin origin, which were canonized by the Catholic Church.

The observation is implemented on the corpus of fifty-four feminine anthroponyms. "Dicționar onomastic românesc" by N. A. Constantinescu and the sites *www.kurufin.ru* and *www.behindthename.com* are used as the main sources of information. All other additional sources of information used in order to complete this research and presented in that text are given at the very end, in *References*, and are cited in *Endnotes*.

Every one of those fifty-three Moldavian and Romanian feminine proper names is derived from another personal name and that is why they are classified according to the main characteristics of the anthroponym, used as a basis during the process of derivation, i. e. whether it is masculine or feminine by gender, or whether it is Latin or Moldavian/Romanian by origin. We distinguish:

(1) Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal names derived from a Roman feminine name: *Agripina* (< *Agrippina* < *Agrippinus* (Roman cognomen)¹), *Beatrice* (< *Beatrix/Viatrix* < *Viator* (late Latin name)²), *Clara* (< *Clara* < *Clarus* (late Latin name)³), *Clementina* (< *Clementina* < *Clementinus* (Roman cognomen)⁴), *Diana* (< *Diana* (the name of the Roman goddess of the moon, hunting, woods and birth-giving; meaning unknown⁵)⁶), *Flora* (< *Flora* (the name of the Roman goddess of the flowers < *flos, floris*)⁷), *Letiția* (< *Laetitia* (late Latin name < *laetitius* ("happy")⁸), *Lucia* (< *Lucia* < *Lucius* (Roman praenomen)⁹), *Monica* (< *Monica* (late Latin name; meaning unknown¹⁰)¹¹), *Natalia* (< *Natalia* (Medieval Latin name < *Natale Domini* ("Christmas Day")¹², from (*dies*) *Natalis* ("Birthday; connected with the birth-

giving")¹³, or from the Latin adjective *natalis, e* ("of birth, natal"¹⁴), *Olivia* (< *Oliva* (late Latin name < *oliva, ae* ("olive")¹⁵), *Petronela* (< *Petronilla* (a diminutive of the Roman feminine name *Petronia*¹⁶) < *Petronius* (Roman family name)¹⁷), *Regina* (< *Regina* (late Latin name < *regina, ae* ("queen")¹⁸), *Renata* (< *Renata* (late Latin name < *renatus* ("reborn, born again")¹⁹), *Roza* (< *Rosa* (late Latin name < *rosa, ae* ("rose")²⁰), *Rozalia* (< *Rosalia* (late Latin name < *rosa, ae* ("rose")²¹), *Tatiana* (< *Tatiana* < *Tatianus* (Roman cognomen)²²), *Violeta* (< *Viola* (late Latin name < *viola, ae* ("violete")²³).

(2) Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal names derived from a Moldavian/Romanian masculine personal name Latin by origin: *Angela* (< *Angel* (late Latin name)²⁴), *Antonina* (< *Antonin* < *Antoninus* (Roman family name, used also as a cognomen)²⁵), *Augustina* (< *Augustin* < *Augustinus* (Roman cognomen)²⁶), *Aurelia* (< *Aurel* < *Aurelius* (Roman family name)²⁷), *Camila* (< *Camil* < *Camillus* (Roman cognomen)²⁸), *Cezara* (< *Cezar* < *Caesar* (Roman cognomen)²⁹), *Claudia* (< *Claudiu* < *Claudius* (Roman family name)³⁰), *Cristiana* (< *Cristian* < *Christianus* (late Latin name)³¹), *Emilia* (< *Emil* < *Aemilius* (Roman family name)³²), *Flavia* (< *Flaviu* < *Flavius* (Roman family name)³³), *Flaviana* (< *Flavian* < *Flavianus* (Roman family name)³⁴), *Floriana* (< *Florian* < *Florianus* (Roman cognomen)³⁵), *Iulia* (< *Iuliu* < *Iulius/Julius* (Roman family name)³⁶), *Iuliana* (< *Iulian* < *Iulianus* (Roman cognomen)³⁷), *Iustina* (< *Iustin* < *Iustinus/Justinus* (Roman cognomen)³⁸), *Laureana* (< *Laurean* < *Laurianus* (late Latin name)³⁹), *Lucreția* (< *Lucrețiu* < *Lucretius* (Roman family name)⁴⁰), *Marcela* (< *Marcel* < *Marcellus* (Roman cognomen)⁴¹), *Mariana* (< *Marian* < *Marianus* (Roman cognomen)⁴²), *Marina* (< *Marin* < *Marinus* (Roman cognomen)⁴³), *Martina* (< *Martin* < *Martinus* (Roman cognomen)⁴⁴), *Paula* (< *Paul* < *Paullus/Paulus* (Roman praenomen, used also as a cognomen)⁴⁵), *Sabina* (< *Sabin* < *Sabinus* (Roman cognomen)⁴⁶), *Silvia* (< *Silviu* < *Silvius* (Roman family name)⁴⁷), *Valentina* (< *Valentin* < *Valentinus* (Roman cognomen)⁴⁸), *Valeria* (< *Valeriu* < *Valerius* (Roman family name)⁴⁹), *Viviana* (< *Vivian* < *Vivianus* (late Latin name)⁵⁰).

(3) Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal names derived from a Moldavian/Romanian feminine personal name of Latin origin: *Cristina* (< *Cristiana* < *Cristian* (Moldavian/Romanian masculine personal name Latin by origin) < *Christianus* (late Latin name)⁵¹).

(4) Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal names derived directly from a Roman masculine name:

- from a Roman family name: *Cecilia* < *Caecilius*⁵²;

- from a Roman cognomen: *Paulina* < *Paulinus*⁵³;
- from a Medieval Latin name: *Laura* < *Laurus*⁵⁴.

(5) names with more than one supposed origin and etymology: *Constanța* (< (1) from the Roman feminine name *Constntia* (< *Constantius* (Roman cognomen))⁵⁵, (2) directly from the Roman masculine names *Constans* and *Constantius* (Roman cognomina)⁵⁶); *Domnica* (< (1) from the Moldavian/Romanian masculine personal name Latin by origin *Dominic* < *Dominicus* (late Latin name)⁵⁷, (2) from the Roman feminine name *Domnica* (diminutive of the Roman feminine name *Domna*)⁵⁸); *Felicia* (< (1) from the Moldavian/Romanian masculine personal name Latin by origin *Felix* < *Felix* (Roman agnomen, i. e. a nickname, used as a second cognomen)⁵⁹, (2) from the Roman feminine name *Felicia* < *Felicius* (Roman cognomen)⁶⁰); *Victoria* (< (1) *Victoria* (the name of the Roman goddess of victory < *victoria, ae* ("victory"))⁶¹, (2) directly from the Latin noun *victoria, ae* ("victory")⁶², (3) from the Roman cognomen *Victorius* < *victor* ("winner")⁶³, (4) from the Roman cognomen *Victor* < *victor* ("winner")⁶⁴).

Another classification can be done in accordance with the very fact if the name is canonized only by the Catholic Church or if it is included in the list of saint names recognized by the Orthodox Church, too:

- names canonized only by the Catholic Church: *Angela, Augustina, Aurelia, Beatrice, Camila, Cezara, Clara, Clementina, Constanța, Cristiana, Felicia, Flavia, Flora, Floriana, Iuliana, Laureana, Letiția, Lucreția, Monica, Olivia, Paulina, Regina, Renata, Roza, Rozalia, Silvia, Victoria, Violeta, Viviana*;

- names canonized by both the Catholic and the Orthodox Churches: *Agripina, Antonina, Cecilia, Claudia, Cristina, Diana, Domnica, Emilia, Flaviana, Iulia, Iustina, Laura, Lucia, Narcela, Mariana, Marina, Martina, Natalia, Paula, Petronela, Sabina, Tatiana, Valentina, Valeria*.

The biggest group is the one which consists of the Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal names that are derived from Moldavian and Romanian masculine personal names of Latin origin (27). The least group includes feminine anthroponyms derived from another Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal name – only one example (*Cristina* < *Cristiana*).

The number of the names derived from a masculine name (30) is bigger than that derived from another feminine anthroponym (19). Four of the names included in the present research are of uncertain etymology and origin. It is so because of the impossibility to find out the way those names have entered the Moldavian and Romanian anthroponimic systems.

Twenty-eight of the observed names are derived from another Moldavian or Romanian name, while twenty-one are derived directly from a Roman

name (eighteen from a feminine Roman name and three from a masculine one).

All the Moldavian and Romanian feminine personal names of Latin origin under consideration in the present text are canonized: twenty-nine by the Catholic Church, while twenty-four are included in the so-called saints' list by both Churches, i. e. the Orthodox and the Catholic ones.

Notes

¹Constantinescu, 1963; www.kurufin.ru.

²www.kurufin.ru.

³www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.

⁴www.kurufin.ru.

⁵It is possible the name to be derived from pre-Indo-European word **deivos* – “god” (www.kurufin.ru), from an Indo-European root meaning “heavenly, divine” (Voinov *et alii*, 1990; www.behindthename.com), from the Latin *deus, i, m* – “god” (Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*; Knappová, 1986), from the feminine form (, i. e. *diviana*) of the Latin *divianus, 3* – “the one, who is divine” (Kovachev, 1995) or from the Latin *dies, diei, m/f* – “day” (<http://slovník.dovrecka.sk/etymologicky-slovník-mien>).

⁶www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.

⁷www.kurufin.ru.

⁸*ibidem*.

⁹Constantinescu, 1963; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.

¹⁰It is supposed that the name is probably derived from the Greek *μόνη* – “single” or from the Latin verb *moneo, 2* – “remind; inspire; foretell” (www.kurufin.ru).

¹¹www.kurufin.ru.

¹²Doichinovich, 2010; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru; <http://slovník.dovrecka.sk/etymologicky-slovník-mien>.

¹³Constantinescu, 1963; Garkovich, 1966; Kol *et alii*, 2011; www.ksiegaimion.com; www.leksykony.interia.pl; <http://slovník.dovrecka.sk/etymologicky-slovník-mien>.

¹⁴Dzyatkovskaya *et alii*, 1986; Ilchev, 1959; Knappová, 1986; Kol *et alii*, 2011; Kovachev, 1995.

¹⁵www.kurufin.ru.

¹⁶Ilchev, 1959; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.

¹⁷www.kurufin.ru.

¹⁸*ibidem*.

¹⁹*ibidem*.

²⁰*ibidem*.

²¹www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.

²²*ibidem*.

²³www.kurufin.ru.

²⁴Constantinescu, 1963; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.

²⁵www.kurufin.ru.

- ²⁶*ibidem.*
- ²⁷www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.
- ²⁸www.kurufin.ru.
- ²⁹*ibidem.*
- ³⁰www.behindthename.com; www.kurufun.ru.
- ³¹www.kurufin.ru.
- ³²www.behindthename.com; www.kurufun.ru.
- ³³*ibidem.*
- ³⁴www.kurufin.ru.
- ³⁵*ibidem.*
- ³⁶www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.
- ³⁷*ibidem.*
- ³⁸Constantinescu, 1963; www.kurufin.ru.
- ³⁹www.kurufin.ru.
- ⁴⁰*ibidem.*
- ⁴¹www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.
- ⁴²*ibidem.*
- ⁴³Constantinescu, 1963; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.
- ⁴⁴www.kurufin.ru.
- ⁴⁵www.behindthename.com; www.kurufun.ru.
- ⁴⁶*ibidem.*
- ⁴⁷*ibidem.*
- ⁴⁸Constantinescu, 1963; www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.
- ⁴⁹*ibidem.*
- ⁵⁰www.kurufin.ru.
- ⁵¹www.behindthename.com; www.kurufin.ru.
- ⁵²www.kurufin.ru.
- ⁵³*ibidem.*
- ⁵⁴www.behindthename.com; www.kurufun.ru.
- ⁵⁵Constantinescu, 1963; www.behindthename.com.
- ⁵⁶www.kurufun.ru.
- ⁵⁷*ibidem.*
- ⁵⁸Constantinescu, 1963.
- ⁵⁹www.kurufun.ru.
- ⁶⁰www.behindthename.com.
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- ⁶²www.behindthename.com.
- ⁶³*ibidem.*
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